

**THE AFRICAN UNION (AU), REGIONAL INTEGRATION
AND THE CHALLENGES OF GLOBALISATION IN THE 21ST
CENTURY**

BY

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Abstract

Globalisation as a complex phenomenon that has increased the interconnectedness of the globe has brought with it both benefits and challenges. In Africa, Globalisation has brought more challenges than benefits to the continent. Africa is in its quest to benefit from globalisation while being marginalised by the international system, leading to many problems and challenges covering areas such as economic, political, social and cultural. This work examines these problems and challenges and was carried out using content analysis on secondary materials. The work is guided by a preposition from the dependency theory that since the advent of globalisation, African states have been marginalised and disadvantaged by the western countries, and this is mostly due to the fact and nature that the African continent is very poor and weak. However, the evolution of the African Union together with some of its new institutions such as NEPAD and APRM is a plausible and welcome development for the continent to address its challenges. Yet, it has become imperative that if at all Africa is to survive the challenges of the 21st century posed by globalisation, African states have to come together and strengthen the institutions, functions as well as the activities of the African Union in order to minimize the adverse effects of globalisation while harnessing whatever its benefit are for a sustainable continental development.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.1 Introduction

The African Union is a continental entity covering the entirety of the African continent. Its origins are the Union of African States, an early confederation that was established by Haile Selassie and Kwame Nkrumah in the 1960s, as well as subsequent attempts to unite Africa, including the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), which was established on May 25, 1963, and the African Economic Community in 1981. The transformation of the Organization of African Unity to the African Union is a progressive landmark in the protracted struggle for African integration, and a call for a new philosophy of African integration in the emerging challenge of globalisation. The Organization of African Unity was guided by two major philosophies: sovereignty of individual states and the non-interference principle. The African Union is, however, challenged to protect the security of the continent. It is important to mention that, to a large extent, OAU was a success because it was able to achieve her primary aims of social existence including acting as a collective voice for the African continent, eradication of all forms of colonialism, and the adoption of non-aligned posture in the bi-polar world order of the Cold War era (Thom-Otuya, 2011).

African Union (AU) was officially launched in July 2002 in Durban, South Africa, following a decision in September 1999 by its predecessor, the OAU, to create a new continental organisation to build on its work. The decision to re-launch the pan-African organisation was the outcome of a consensus by African leaders that in order to realise Africa's potential in the new century, there was a need to refocus attention from the fight for decolonisation and ridding the continent of apartheid, which had been the focus of the OAU, towards increased cooperation and integration of African states to drive Africa's growth and economic development.

The integration of African States has been a lingering issue right from the birth of OAU. During her initial formation, African States were polarized into three different ideological groups: These were the Casablanca bloc made up of Ghana, Guinea, Morocco, Egypt, Mali and Libya; Monrovia bloc made up of Nigeria, Senegal, Ethiopia, Liberia, Tunisia and Togo; and the Brazzaville bloc which was made up of majority of the French speaking countries. These tripartite divisions were later reduced to two blocks: the Casablanca and Monrovia blocs. The Casablanca bloc (Olukoshi, 2010) was led by Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana. They wanted a rapid movement by

independent African countries towards a politically united and economically integrated framework. The Monrovia group was often represented by Abubakar Tafawa Balewa of Nigeria. They were for a much more gradualist approach by which unity and integration would be achieved through small and incremental steps.

Globalisation is the process of interaction and integration between people, companies, and governments worldwide. Similarly, globalisation is the multiplicity of linkages that allows free flow of ideas, people, and goods and services across boundaries without restriction. Globalisation has grown due to advances in transportation and communication technology. With increased global interactions comes the growth of international trade, ideas, and culture. Globalisation is primarily an economic process of interaction and integration that is associated with social and cultural aspects. However, conflicts and diplomacy are also large parts of the history of globalisation. Globalisation is not a new phenomenon in the world, and many countries have sought to gain from it. In Africa, the continent began to be integrated into the global economic system in the sixteenth century, and this integration has proceeded steadily, though unevenly, since that time. However, it was in the early 1990s that globalisation was received with excitement, since capital flows had increased six folds in six years, from 1990 to 1996 (International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook). Globalisation of the world economy, especially in the areas of trade, production and finance, has made the world more interconnected and integrated. This has led to the weakening of the autonomy of states since financial markets are volatile in nature and affect national economies. The third world countries seem to have been marginalized and left behind by globalisation. Globalisation has seriously affected many third world countries particularly those in Africa, in economic, political, security, health, social, and cultural areas.

The ultimate view on the role of globalisation on the African economies is likely to be unresolved for a long time, partly because continuing studies do not affirm either or refute the other, or because most of these sensational views are merely based on ideological affiliations. Ibrahim (2013) outlines the vices of globalisation on African economies including dictatorial leaders, social conflicts and international tensions like the Cold War, which outcomes further inhibit full scale appropriation of the benefits of globalisation. On the same note, Ajayi (2003) argues that the present condition of African economies is the outcome of their own isolation from the global markets through market controls and unwelcome policy regimes.

Available evidence suggests that Africa is the second most unequal continent in the world next to Latin America (e.g. Ravallion and Chen, 2012). High inequality also seems to have persisted over time with no visible sign of declining (Bigsten, 2014; Milanovic, 2003). On top of this, many multinational corporations do not even sell African products using prices established by the laws of supply and demand in a free market. Increased costs of production are not passed onto the consumers who buy the produce, instead they are sold from the source in Africa at a lower rate which means less income for African workers and business. The global market also sets a price for most Africa's exports and so the higher production cost cannot be recovered. At the same time, a rise in productivity will not necessarily lower world prices by an increase in supply, because the demand may remain small. Africa has mostly been caught in this economic cycle. This is a fundamental inequality in international trade and once this has been set up it is difficult to change.

Clearly, Africa and globalisation have had a long and unhappy history together. Capitalist globalisation undeniably created wealth but also intensified inequality, underdevelopment and poverty in Africa. Indeed, there is a positive functional relationship between globalisation and many challenges in Africa.

However, for states to resist these pressures, they pursued regional integration. Regional integration has been the most appropriate measure to fight the challenges of globalisation in developing countries due to their nature in terms of economic output. In Africa, the African Union was established. Still, it has become imperative that if at all Africa is to survive the current challenges posed by globalisation, African states must come together and strengthen the functions, policies and activities of the African Union to minimize the adverse effects of globalisation while harnessing whatever its benefits are for continental development.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

Africa is the least integrated within the world economy. While developing countries increased their share of world trade from 19 percent in 1971 to 29 percent in 1999, Africa performed poorly with its share of world trade being less than 2 percent in 1999. Specifically, the share of Africa's trade as global trade fell from some 3 percent in 1960 to 1.6 percent in 1997. Besides, Africa was the only major region in the world to experience an absolute decline in export earnings per person between 1980 and 1996 (Sachs and Sievers 1999:13).

The forces of globalisation which to Africa and beyond increased the interconnectedness of the world have brought both benefits and challenges. These forces, such as trade liberalization and technological advancement, while benefitting others, especially the developed states, have become a major challenge to developing countries, especially those in Africa.

Africa, in its quest to benefit from globalisation while being marginalized, has lost its stance in the international system. Africa as part of the least integrated in world economy, derives the least benefits from globalisation since Africa has been the underdog of the global economy. As other regions in the world are experiencing one form of development through globalisation, Africa on its part is experiencing a multifaceted developmental problem through the same instrument of globalisation.

This problem has affected and is still affecting the continent politically, economically, and socially. In the light of this, this research work is designed to enumerate all the problems bedeviling Africa because of globalisation.

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the circumstances that led to the establishment of the African Union (AU)?
2. What is globalisation and how does it affect regional integration in Africa?
3. What other challenges does globalisation pose to Africa's quest for regional integration in the 21st century?

1.4 Objectives of the Research

The main objective of this research is to examine the challenges which globalisation poses on regional integration in Africa about the African Union. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To study the circumstances that led to the establishment of the African Union (AU).
2. To discuss globalisation and how it affects regional integration in Africa.
3. To discuss other challenges that globalisation poses to Africa's quest for regional integration in the 21st century.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research is significant because it will contribute to the existing literature on African Union, regional integration, and the impacts which globalisation has on the African continent. It will also serve as an additional academic work to institutions like the African Union, National

Institute of International Affairs (NIA), non-governmental organizations, policy makers and other interested individuals that are concerned with African politics and development.

1.6 Scope and Limitation

Contextually, the study focuses on African Union, regional integration and the impacts which globalisation has on the African continent.

Specifically on the limitation, virtually all research is often confronted with one constraint or another. This research work will therefore not be an exemption. In producing a work like this, the problem that confronted the researcher was not the scarcity of materials, but its availability. The researcher encountered some constraints, which limited the scope of the study. The main limitations of this research, however, are:

a) **Availability of Research Material:** The research material available to the researcher is insufficient, thereby limiting the study.

b) **Time:** The time frame allocated to the study does not enhance wider coverage as the researcher has to combine other academic activities and examinations with the study.

These, however, would place a constraint to the method of analysis available for this study, its high cost of sourcing material, the lack of important literature texts and time constraints within which this study must be carried out.

1.7 Methodology

According to Coten and Manion (1980), method refers to the range of approaches used in research to gather data which are to be used as a basis for inference and interpretation, for explanation and prediction. However, the word method can be referred to as those techniques associated with the scientific model such as eliciting responses to predetermined questions, recording measurements, describing phenomena and performing experiments (Obasi, 1999).

To this study, the method of data collection employed is qualitative in nature. The qualitative method of data collection mainly involves the use of secondary sources of data. This is because secondary sources of data involve the use of existing data collected for the purposes of prior study to pursue a research interest which is distinct from that of the original work. This may be a new research question or an alternative perspective on the original question (Hindes, Vogel

and Clerk-Stiffen 1997; Szabo and Strang 1997). Basically, secondary sources of data include data that has already been collected and recorded by someone else and readily available from other sources like the internet, textbooks, magazines, journals, etc. (Johnston 2014; Tran Thi Ut 2013). The secondary sources of data employed in this work include information from textbooks, journals, magazines, internet materials, seminars, debates and seminar publications.

Qualitative data can be observed and recorded. This data type is non-numerical in nature. This type of data is collected through methods of observations, one-to-one interviews, conducting focus groups, and similar methods.

1.8 Method of Data Analysis

Data analysis can be defined as the breaking down and ordering of collection of information obtained through research (Asika, 1991). The qualitative descriptive analysis is applied in this study; it connotes the summary of the information generated in the research. In most cases, the description may make use of some qualitative information, but in most cases, it does not make use of quantitative information (Asika, 1991). Bogdan and Biklen (1982) noted that it involves working with data, organizing it, breaking it into manageable units, synthesizing it, searching for patterns, discovering what is important and what is to be learned and deciding what you will tell others. More so, the descriptive qualitative analysis is used in this research because it summarizes the information generated in the research. Also, there are further searches for trends and patterns of association and relationships among the variables collected without the use of frequency distribution, measures of central tendency and measures of dispersion.

1.9 Organization of Chapters

This work is arranged in five chapters:

Chapter one lays the foundation of the research topic by introducing the study in its entirety, drawing attention on the study problem, objectives, and significance of the study, together with methodology and theoretical framework on how this research will be carried out.

Chapter two consists of the literature review which entails some analysis of the subject matter as undertaken by different scholars.

Chapter three provides a historical overview of the antecedents that led to the formation of the African Union.

Chapter four entails the research findings on “African Union, regional integration and challenges of globalisation in Africa”.

Chapter five is the concluding part which encompasses the summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Introduction

The literature on African Union, regional integration and globalisation is largely treated as separate subjects. The literature review will focus around three key areas: the conceptualisation of globalisation, globalisation and Africa, and the evolution of the African Union (AU) with its ability to promote regional integration.

2.2.1 The Concept of Globalisation

Globalisation is a phenomenon that is multi-dimensional and multi-faceted in nature. It has economic, political, social, and cultural implications. Scholars have variously referred to it as modernization, internationalization, universalization, liberalization, among other nomenclatures.

The Economic Commission for Africa (2000) has remarked that globalisation refers to the changes occurring at the global level, which in several ways have not been in the control of individual nation states and their government (Africa, 2000). In line with this, Yunusa pointed out that it is all about greater interaction among countries and people. He, however, fears that this integration is dangerous because of inequalities existing between developed and developing countries (Yunusa, 2004).

Tomlinson (1996) therefore noted that globalisation is a rapidly developing process of complex interconnection between societies, cultures, institutions and individuals worldwide. It is a social process which involves a compression of time and space, shrinking distances through dramatic reduction in time taken either physically or representational to cross those, so making the world seem smaller and in a certain sense bringing human beings closer to one another.

Verables P. Krugman (1995) described globalisation as the “contemporary pretender” of imperialism. Like imperialism, globalisation is shown to be having profound and intrusive impacts, especially on weaker societies. It also magnified the inequality of capitalist expansion. It has been the philosophy of WTO, IMF and World Bank whom African scholars have always referred to as agents of imperialism.

2.2.2 Globalisation and Africa

According to Khor, in the process of globalisation, developing countries, particularly African countries, have been marginalized, their options limited by institutionalized global regime for the collection of global available resources. This imbalance leads to polarization between the few countries and groups that gain and the many countries and groups in societies that lose out or are marginalized.

The greatest area of the impact of globalisation on African societies and on the people is in the areas where the state used to play significant roles in the life of the people through social welfare policies and programmes. Cancellation of these policies and withdrawal of such welfare programmes and uncontrolled adoption and promotion of market reforms significantly weakens socio-economic equilibrium in developing societies. Depending on the capacity of the state, all these interactions create a dynamic set of forces that in certain cases provoke turbulence, serious instability, and possible disintegration and without measures to cushion the effects of these drastic economic reforms, African societies were put under severe economic and social stress, further undermining political stability and social harmony. There is no doubt whatsoever that globalisation is one of the challenges confronting development in world history (Tando, 1998).

Jeffrey Herbst (2007) in his work *Africa and the Challenge of Globalisation* says that globalisation is not a new concept, tracing its origins as far back as the slave trade. He goes further to discuss how globalisation is irreversible and has come to stay. Herbst blames Africa's inability to fully profit from globalisation on its difficult geography, dependence on raw material and natural disasters. This makes it difficult for Africa to compete globally. However, the major challenge is governance crisis which has prevented African countries from participating and integrating into the international economy. The author concludes that for African countries to benefit from globalisation, they must improve on their poor brand image, develop comparative advantage in relatively labor-intensive manufacturing, develop a political consensus around growth, and insulate themselves from neighboring troubles.

Herbst's work is relevant to the current work because it tries to outline the challenges being faced by Africa in its quest to benefit from globalisation. It also makes some suggestions on how to fully benefit from globalisation. However, Herbst fails to acknowledge the African efforts particularly in the realm of African Union to address the challenges of globalisation in Africa. For

example, bad governance is set to be addressed through the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) and African Peer Review Mechanism (APRM) initiatives by the African Union (AU).

2.2.3 The Evolution of the African Union (AU)

The establishment of the Organization of African Unity (OAU) and later African Union (AU) was a subject area that seized the attention of many scholars who wrote widely about its inception and reasons for its establishment as set forth by African States which essentially were to deal effectively with the challenges facing the African continent, including those of globalisation.

The OAU was founded in 1963 as a regional organisation amidst great hope and optimism. But those positive expectations were ragged by Cold War with colonial, neocolonial and imperialist exploitation, ideological diversities, political instability, financial problems and frequent and reoccurring wars and conflicts internally and externally within the African continent. It therefore became expedient that if Africa is to survive, develop, and address its current and upcoming challenges particularly in the 21st century drastic measures must be adopted. It is in the light of this that the African Union was created and constituted to replace the OAU. Many scholars have studied the evolution of the new organisation (AU), its functions, institutions and strategies to deal with the challenges facing the continent including that of globalisation (Mkinda and Okumu, 2006).

For example, the African Union during its inauguration in 2002 set for itself the ambition of building, by the year 2025:

“A united and integrated Africa; an Africa imbued with the ideals of justice and peace; an inter-dependent and virile Africa determined to map for itself an ambitious strategy; an Africa underpinned by political, economic, social and cultural integration which would restore Pan-Africanism its full meaning; an Africa able to make the best of its human and material resources, and keen to ensure the progress and prosperity of its citizens by taking advantage of the opportunities offered by a globalized world; an Africa engaging in promoting its values in a world rich in its disparities.”

Furthermore, Van de Walle observes that the African Union is an organisation that genuinely reflects the aspiration of tens of millions of Africans for continental unity (Walle, 2001).

Agubuzu (2002) in his book *From the OAU to AU: the challenges of African unity and development in the 21st century* opined that the African Union provided for a loose confederation or association of states, whose members undertook the process of coordinating and harmonizing their general policies through cooperation in the political, diplomatic, economic, communication, health, sanitation, nutrition, scientific and technological spheres, as well as through cooperation in defense and security, and border control.

In the economic field, the Union achieved part of its commitment. As Agubuzu further submitted that at the level of economic integration, cooperation and development, there emerged over the past 40 years under the OAU, several regional and sub-regional economic groupings reflecting an acceptance of transnational, state-led economic cooperation or integration, involving the pooling of common resources in response to shared problems and opportunities. As a matter of fact, not much was achieved by the OAU in terms of substantive unity or the protection of human rights in Africa. This was mainly because of the unwillingness of the heads of state and governments to match their rhetoric with action (Agubuzu, 2002).

In line with this, Mkinda and Okumu (2006) in their paper “The African Union: Past and Future Governance Challenges” drew analysis of the difficulties faced by African leaders in addressing the challenges faced in the organizational setups, given the change from the OAU to the AU. The authors stressed that one of the main obstacles towards the achievement of the Union objectives included the advent of globalisation. Africa is yet to fully adopt the change that comes with globalisation due to the myriads of problems faced by Africa. This has been attributed to the lack of regional approaches to solving issues faced by countries within the continent and as such, Africa is yet to fully benefit from the potential that globalisation carries with it.

This above view was also supported by Akokpari, Ndinga-Muvumba and Murithi (2008) in their book *The African Union and its Institutions*. They argued that the challenges being faced by the AU include those of development which have been aggravated by the advent of globalisation. They further argue that even though the AU had made progressive steps towards addressing these challenges, the transformation of the blueprint vision into reality seems to be very difficult. To them, the AU does afford Africa the opportunity to take on these challenges. However, they failed to highlight the AU efforts in the reformation of organisational institutional structure which will henceforth enable the Union to be more committed to African problems as well as

achieve the organisation's objectives. The AU came at the ideal time as the perfect instrument for implementing the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) and bringing about an age of prosperity and progress. The African Union provided a common platform and unity to the member states which enabled them to acquire a common voice, although still a weak one in the international community (Tilley, 2000).

2.3 Theoretical Framework

This work is framed within the dependency theory. Notable proponents of the dependency theory include Hans Singer (1978), Raul Prebisch (1996), and Andre Gunder Frank (1990). Dependency theory originates with two papers published in 1949, one by Hans Singer and the other by Raul Prebisch, in which the authors observe that the terms of trade for underdeveloped countries relative to the developed countries had deteriorated over time. The underdeveloped countries were able to purchase fewer manufactured goods from the developed countries in exchange for a given quantity of their raw materials exports (Balassa, 1967).

The central thesis of the theory is the notion that resources flow from a periphery (satellites) of poor and underdeveloped states to a "core" (metropole) of wealthy states, enriching the latter at the expense of the former. It is the central contention of the dependency theory that poor states are impoverished, and rich ones are enriched by the way poor states are integrated into the "world system." The periphery or satellite in this context is the African states while the core and metropole signify the states of Western Europe and Northern America (Balassa, 1967).

According to Andre Gunder Frank, the failure of the satellite is because of the incorporation of satellites into world capitalist economy which led to international division of labour whereby the less developed nations like African states provided food and raw materials for the great industrial centre. This relationship led to the perpetual exploitation of both human and material resources, hegemony and subjugation of African states (Frank, 1969).

Andre Gunder Frank, in his hypothetical analysis of the unequal relationship between the satellite and metropole asserted that satellite states experience great economic development when their relationship with the metropolitan area is weak. Development of satellites is choked as soon as the relationship between the satellite and metropolis is normalized. The regime that was underdeveloped, feudal and backward had close ties with the metropolitan area.

Therefore, the unequal relationship between the African Union member states and metropolis had rather entrapped them in heavy debt burden or rather massive political and economic crisis. For example, the policy of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) led to a situation where African states deepened its authoritarianism, they brazenly violated citizen's right and increasingly became high-handed in its dealings with society. Therefore, at any rate, SAP could not have mitigated African economic crisis in any significant way since it was consciously designed to manage African crisis more in a way that served the economic interest of the West than in exiting the continent from crisis and its attendant underdevelopment.

Africa's political, economic and socio-cultural crises are consequences of the activities of the alien forces from the West (metropole) whose desire for self-sustenance and preservation is connected to African resources. As such, it is deliberate for them to distort the social formation of Africa and to make their quest for unity and development elusive. Furthermore, Africa has become killing field due to proliferation of weapons from the West, the intention of the West behind all these is to stampede any effort towards reconciliation and peace as requisite for economic development.

The international division of labour where Africa produced raw materials for industries in Europe and America was deliberately orchestrated to make Africa perpetually dependent on the metropolis. It is not just enough for African Union (AU) and African leaders to come up with new continental political organization, protocols, legal instruments and charters to champion the course for African development, a lot must be done on our psyche or orientation decolonization of the mind. It suffices to say then, that the emergence of globalisation in the context of liberalization and free markets became the new paradigm. Although originally dependency theorists argued that the ideal way to break out of the dependency trap and end global inequality is for the periphery to separate from the core, the post-Cold War era led to further regional integration rather than separation (Sekhri, 2009, p. 242).

2.4 Conclusion

To sum up, Africa's political, economic and socio-cultural crises are mainly the consequences of the activities of the alien forces from the West (metropole) whose desire for self-sustenance and preservation is connected to African resources. As such, it is deliberate for them to distort the social formation of Africa and to make their quest for unity and development elusive.

Therefore, true and complete independence of Africa can only be achieved through unity, cooperation and support among all African states. The African Union is beginning to bring meaningful development to the continent; however, there is more that is needed to be done by African leaders in curbing and curtailing the effects of neo-colonialism and imperialism in all its manifestations and ramifications.

CHAPTER THREE

FORMATION OF THE AFRICAN UNION (AU): A HISTORICAL OVERVIEW

3.1 Introduction

One of the geographic features of the earth is its division into political units. At a very broad level, the world is divided into continents, namely: Africa, Antarctica, Asia, Australia, Oceania, North America, South America and Europe. The African continent in the late nineteenth century contained a vast mosaic of tribal peoples who lived in a varied landscape of desert, rain forest, savannah, mountain, and coastal lands. All these peoples had adapted their social and economic organizations to their environments, and their political systems varied from large empires to tribal groupings under chieftains.

For several centuries, from the eleventh century to the nineteenth century, Africa was the object of Arab and European political incursion and domination. Although such a predatory relationship existed even among groups within the continent, the nineteenth and twentieth-century European imperialism was particularly unique in being brutal, with colonialism based on a mixture of economic, strategic, cultural, and nationalistic spearheading motives. European imperialism expressed itself in the partition of the African continent and the subsequent colonization. Apart from the disruption or destruction of many traditional African societies, Europeans in Africa extensively exploited the continent's mineral and agricultural products, often by means of forced labour.

After several decades of subjugation, Africa began to move from a continent of colonies to a continent of independent states in the period after the Second World War (1939–1945), although the nationalist struggles for independence were often impeded or undercut by the complex mosaic of differing ethnic, linguistic, and religious communities, which made unification difficult. With the establishment of modern states in Africa based on artificial national boundaries devised by the European powers, which produced a national consciousness based on European colonial territories, the idea of continental unity became a major issue among the various nationalist leaders. This culminated in the founding of the African Union in 2002.

However, in order to understand the historical evolution of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU)/African Union (AU), there is the need to first understand the terms Pan-Africanism and Pan-African Congresses which were considered as the founding stones of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), the African Union (AU) and any other failed attempt at political and economic integration between and among African states.

3.2 Pan-Africanism

The first step in the formation of the African Union was the conceptualization of the idea of Pan-Africanism. The African Union is the inevitable historical maturation of the ideas of Pan-Africanism and Pan-African unity, which gave rise to the establishment of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) and the African Union (AU). It was a movement that advocated the unity of Africans in the diaspora and mainland Africa (Agubuzu, 2002).

Thompson defines Pan-Africanism as a political movement based on colour consciousness among blacks in the diaspora. Its proponents were of the view that the ancestral home of all black peoples throughout the world was the African continent. Pan-Africanism became the rallying cry for all Africans in the diaspora to unite and fight against discrimination in their host countries as well as a tool to link them with their fellow Africans on the mainland (Thompson, 1969).

The pioneers of Pan-Africanism saw the movement as a manifestation of fraternal solidarity among Africans and the peoples of African descent. At the turn of the twentieth century, the movement asserted that Africans could no longer tolerate being dominated and manipulated politically. They stood against the marginalization of Africans by external powers and asserted that African interests should be paramount. Africans in the colonies were therefore urged by those in the diaspora to work hard to liberate themselves.

3.3 The Pan-African Congresses

The Pan-Africanist movement went through different phases of development and institutionalization. The evolution of the movement began with the Pan-African Congresses at which leaders like Henry Sylvester Williams, Marcus Garvey and W.E.B. Du Bois espoused ideas that later formed the basis for policies that culminated in the founding of the OAU in May 1963.

The first five Pan-Africanist congresses took place between 1900 and 1927. These congresses called for Africans on the mainland to have a say in their own governments. They

stressed that democratic principles of governance should apply to both blacks and Europeans, whether they were in Europe or in Africa. The congresses further pressed for colonial rule to be dismantled for decolonization to take place and for self-government for Africans.

The landmark congress that triggered the institutionalization of Pan-Africanism was the sixth congress that took place in 1945 in Manchester. The Manchester congress sent a clear message to the colonial powers that Africans would no longer tolerate colonialism on the continent (Murithi, 2005).

3.4 African Nationalism

The 1945 Congress in Manchester, as already noted, introduced would-be leaders to the helm of affairs of the Pan-Africanist Movement who were from the mainland (West, East, Southern Africa and the West Indies). From West Africa emerged leaders like Kwame Nkrumah of Ghana, Nnamdi Azikiwe of Nigeria and Wallace Johnson of Sierra Leone. From East Africa, Jomo Kenyatta of Kenya, and Peter Abrahams and Marko Hlubi from Southern Africa. Those from the West Indies included George Padmore who later became a prominent figure in the Pan-African Movement.

By 1946, African intellectuals and leaders of trade unions had also bought into the ideology of African nationalism through their association with the movement. The main objectives of the African nationalists were the liberation of the continent from European domination and colonization and the eventual unity of the continent (Murithi, 2005).

3.5 The Birth of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU)

Two schools of thought had emerged from the Pan-Africanists involvement in the 1950s and the 1960s that were fiercely debated by the African nationalists. Orobola Fasheh (2005) recounts that one group of nationalists preferred political integration at the continental level, while the second group preferred unity in economic, social and cultural terms at the sub-regional level. At the second All-African Peoples' Conference (AAPC) held in Tunis, these two schools crystallized into two blocs and two distinct approaches to the institutionalization of Pan-Africanism emerged. The moderates, dominated by Nigeria, Ivory Coast, Ethiopia and the French speaking countries advocated for a gradualist approach to African unity. The second group, led by Ghana and Guinea, called for a political union and the creation of a United States of Africa.

The vision of a United States of Africa was, however, not supported by all, and not as radically as Nkrumah, Sékou Touré of Guinea and Modibo Keita of Mali would have preferred. Despite a common vision, differing ideological commitments and diverging opinions regarding strategy and structuring of a continental organisation, they soon divided and obstructed the pursuit of unity. The division led to the emergence of three ideological blocs on the African continent, split between the Casablanca Group (consisting of Ghana, Guinea, Mali, Libya, Egypt, Morocco and Algeria) which advocated for radical and full continental integration, the Monrovia Group (consisting of Nigeria, Tunisia, Ethiopia, Liberia, Sudan, Togo, and Somalia) which proposed a moderate approach to unification to be undertaken in incremental steps, and the Brazzaville Group (consisting of Francophone countries and led by Senegal and Ivory Coast) which remained tied to the interests of France.

Several African leaders, including Kenya's Julius Nyerere and Nigeria's Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, were supportive of the ideal of African unity, but many felt that Nkrumah's grand vision for a United States of Africa was overreaching and ran the risk of dissolving sovereignty and territorial integrity. By the time the OAU was established, it presented itself as a diluted version of its formerly envisioned grandeur.

To achieve consensus to convene a conference that embraced all African states, the Ethiopian Emperor, Haile Selassie, embarked on a mission to reconcile the Casablanca and Monrovia Groups. Ethiopia succeeded in convincing all the thirty-two independent African states to attend the Summit scheduled for May 1963. The institutionalization of the Pan-Africanist Movement was therefore concluded in May 1963 in Addis Ababa with the establishment of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU).

3.5.1 Objectives of the OAU

The objectives of the OAU, just like its principles, were a compromise between the radicals and the moderates. Article 2 of the Charter listed the objectives of the Organisation to include, among others, that the OAU:

- Shall promote the unity and solidarity of African states;
Shall coordinate and intensify their cooperation and efforts to achieve a better life for the people of Africa

- Shall defend the sovereignty of member states, their territorial integrity and independence
- Shall eradicate all forms of colonialism from Africa; and
- Shall promote international cooperation, with special regard to the Charter of the United Nations and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

3.5.2 Organs of the OAU

Article 7 of the OAU Charter states the organs of the Organisation to include:

The Assembly of Heads of State and Government;

The Council of Ministers;

The Secretariat;

The Commission of Mediation, Conciliation and Arbitration;

The Specialized Committees.

3.6 The Transformation of Organisation of African Unity (OAU) to the African Union (AU)

The post-Cold War international system brought pressures of unrestrained globalisation on an increasingly poor African continent in need of a new development paradigm. The OAU lost credibility in the 1990s due to accusations of indifference, bureaucratic paralysis, and failure to address issues of peace, security and governance. Member states were deemed to have perpetrated gross violations of human rights, with high intensity civil wars and genocide occurring within the continent.

As early as 1979, the OAU identified the need to amend its Charter to streamline the Organisation and gear it more accurately for the challenges of the changing world. At the Algiers Summit in July 1999, Colonel Muammar Gaddafi of Libya extended an invitation to the Heads of State and Government of the OAU to attend an Extraordinary Summit in Sirte, Libya. The Summit ended with the adoption of the Sirte Declaration, which focused on strengthening the continental Organisation to cope with political, economic and social developments within and outside the continent.

To achieve these objectives, the Summit decided to establish an African Union in conformity with the ultimate objectives of the Charter of the Continental Organisation and the provisions of the Treaty establishing the African Economic Community (AEC).

Three Summits were held between 1999 and 2002 which facilitated the implementation of the African Union. The Lomé Summit of 2000 adopted the Constitutive Act. The Lusaka Summit of 2001 drew the roadmap for implementation. The Durban Summit of 2002 officially launched the African Union.

3.6.1 Objectives of the AU

The fundamental objectives of the AU, though including a few from the OAU Charter, are more comprehensive. Article 3 of the Constitutive Act specifies the Union's objectives as follows:

Achieve greater unity and solidarity between African countries and the people of Africa;
Defend the sovereignty, territorial integrity and independence of its Member States;
Accelerate the political and socio-economic integration of the continent;
Promote and defend African common positions on issues of interest to the continent and its peoples.

- I. Promote peace, security and stability on the continent.
- II. Promote democratic principles and institutions, popular participation and good governance.
- III. Promote and protect human and people's rights.
- IV. Promote sustainable development at economic, social and cultural levels.
- V. Coordinate and harmonize policies between existing and future Regional Economic Communities.

3.6.2 The Institutional Structure of the African Union (AU)

The African Union inherited many of the institutions of the OAU but committed itself to creating a stronger institutional structure. In addition to the organs of the OAU, the AU Constitutive Act created additional institutions including:

- I. The Pan-African Parliament.
- II. The Court of Justice.
- III. The Technical Committees.
- IV. Financial Institutions.

3.7 Regional Integration in Africa

It is widely acknowledged that Africa's integration efforts have thus far failed to bear satisfactory fruit (Asante, 2007). While other regions have successfully used their integration mechanisms to improve their economic welfare, Africa lags with respect to GDP growth, per capita income, capital inflows, and general living standards. This is a problem across most of the continent, despite the existence of a plethora of policy plans and grand visions.

The formation of regional blocs and groupings has progressively become a prominent feature of world politics since the end of the Second World War (Olubomehin and Kawonishe, 2004). Regional integration generally involves a complex web of cooperation between countries within a given geographical area to harmonize policies in such sectors as trade, investment, infrastructure, as well as monetary and fiscal policies of member states.

There has been much support for the economic integration of African states since independence. This received a great deal of impetus following severe economic instability of the 1970s (Asante, 1999). According to Hartzenberg (2011), the ambition of African leaders to integrate Africa provided the rationale for the Lagos Plan of Action (LPA). Both the LPA (1980) and the Abuja Treaty of 1991 became the agenda for integration based on solidarity and self-reliance. The treaties also called for the creation of regional integration arrangements as starting points for the continent's integration.

According to Asante (2000), ECOWAS is the most concrete African initiative in this direction. ECOWAS is a regional group of fifteen West African countries established on 28 May 1975 under the Treaty of Lagos. It represents a regional institutional framework for the coordination and promotion of economic cooperation in West Africa. Since its inception, ECOWAS has done remarkably well, especially in the areas of peace and security, trade, and the free movement of people and goods in the region. However, the community is faced with several challenges which are likely to impede the effective exercise of its functions and the fulfillment of its purpose. Considering the growing importance of regional integration in the world, it is important therefore to identify the challenges and prospects for regional integration in West Africa.

3.8 Background on Globalisation

Globalisation is a complex, elusive and controversial term. It has been used to refer to a process, a policy, a marketing strategy, a predicament or even an ideology. Globalisation, regardless of its forms or impact, forges connections between previously unconnected people, communities, institutions and societies.

Held et al (1999) defined globalisation as “the widening, intensifying, speeding up, and growing impact of world-wide interconnectedness.” It is the emergence of a complex web of interconnectedness that means that our lives are increasingly shaped by events that occur, and decisions that are made, at a great distance from us. The central feature of globalisation is therefore that geographical distance is of declining relevance and that territorial borders, such as those between nation states, are becoming less significant.

By no means, however, does globalisation imply that the local and the national are subordinated to the global. Rather, it highlights the deepening as well as the broadening of the political process, in the sense that local, national and global events constantly interact. Globalisation has several dimensions or faces. Although globalisation theorists have championed interpretations of globalisation, these are by no means mutually exclusive. Instead, they capture different aspects of a complex and multifaceted phenomenon.

Globalisation has been interpreted in three main ways:

Economic globalisation

Economic globalisation refers to the process whereby all national economies have, to a greater or lesser extent, been absorbed into an interlocking global economy.

Cultural globalisation

Cultural globalisation is the process whereby information, commodities and images that have been produced in one part of the world enter into a global flow that tends to flatten out cultural differences between nations, regions and individuals. Cultural globalisation is closely linked to and emerged in association with economic globalisation and the communication and information revolution.

Political globalisation

Political globalisation refers to the growing importance of international organizations. These are organizations that are transnational in that they exert influence not within a single state, but within an international area comprising several states. However, the nature of political globalisation and its implications for the state varies depending on whether it is modeled on the principle of intergovernmentalism or supranationalism. Most commentators nevertheless accept that political globalisation lags markedly behind economic and cultural forms of globalisation.

3.9 Conclusion

The transformation of the OAU into the AU in 2002 was to reform the old Organisation and make it more effective so as to meet the challenges of the 21st century. It is expected that Africa will begin the new millennium with a resurgent and reinvigorated enthusiasm to develop and enable the continent to play its rightful role in the global economy and international affairs.

CHAPTER FOUR

AFRICAN UNION, GLOBALISATION, AND THE CHALLENGES OF REGIONAL INTEGRATION

4.1 Introduction

Globalisation as the process of intensification of economic, political, social and cultural relations across international boundaries aimed at the uplifting homogenization of political and socio-economic theory across the globe impacts significantly on African states through systematic restructuring of interactive phases among its nations by breaking down barriers in the areas of culture, commerce, communication and several other fields of endeavor. These processes have impelled series of cumulative and conjectural crisis in the international division of labour and global distribution of economic and political power, thereby qualifying basic African features to be marginalized, underdeveloped, poverty-stricken, squalor-ridden and unemployment-prone among other crises.

Africa and globalisation have had a long and unhappy history together. The African continent, due to globalisation, has been marginalized and left behind and this has, in turn, accentuated poverty and economic inequality. Moreover, specific impact of globalisation on Africa has been identified in the political sphere. The most important consequence is the erosion of sovereignty, especially on economic and financial matters, because of external pressures from international financial institutions and global economic forces.

4.2 Globalisation and Economical Challenges in Africa

The area of economy remains crucial in the discussion of the impact of globalisation on Africa. Globalisation has, overall, reinforced the economic marginalization of African economies and their dependence on a few primary goods for which demand and prices are externally determined. This has, in turn accentuated poverty and economic inequality as well as the ability of the vast number of Africans to participate meaningfully in the social and political life of their countries.

The policies of liberalization, privatization and deregulation as well as other associated packages of macro-economic policies imposed through structural adjustment

conditionality/programme by the IMF and World Bank, which have now been institutionalized within the WTO through rules, agreements and procedures, are biased against African countries.

Perhaps nowhere is globalisation more pernicious and debilitating to the interest of Africa than the hugely unfair trade practices institutionalized under the aegis of WTO, by favoring the worst form of unregulated capitalism in modern history, with rigged rules and unfair agricultural standards for Africa, globalisation imperils both democracy and development on the continent.

The rules of the WTO though are put in place to ensure worldwide competition by requiring countries not to discriminate between domestic products, companies, services and intellectual property rights. These rules on the other hand had set standards for the continued marginalization of African countries in world trade in the following areas: Developed countries give less market access to products from developing countries and tend to impose high tariffs on products most valuable to Africa, for instance, textiles and agricultural products.

Developed countries have not been able to completely phase out restrictions for textiles and clothing exports which make it difficult for African producers to compete effectively. The agreement on agriculture has led to competition between subsidized farm products from developed countries and unsubsidized agricultural products from Africa. The enforcement of trade related intellectual property rights (TRIPS) has made technology and essential goods too expensive for developing countries, which in turn increased their dependence on developed economy.

From the above, we can easily argue that globalisation undeniably created wealth but also intensified inequality, underdevelopment and poverty in third world countries, particularly the African countries. However, this pace of globalisation, coupled with the sweeping wave of economic liberalization, and with the imbalances in the distribution of the benefits in favor of the strong economies, has increased the urgency for African countries to join hands to expand, fortify, solidify and integrate their economic space, to serve as a platform for takeoff and effective Africa through the African Union into the global economy. The contemporary African Union therefore at the very least constitutes Africa's response to globalisation, and an instrument to reverse the trend towards the marginalization of the Continent.

4.3 Globalisation and Political Challenges in Africa

Globalisation is more than just economic reality. In fact, it has a significant political dimension as it imposes liberal democracy as the only model of political modernity.

Since the triumph of liberal democracy and capitalism in the early 1990's, democracy became the most acceptable and preferred system of governance in the global system. Therefore, democratization of international politics has become one of the major principles of contemporary globalisation.

However, African countries have for decades witnessed arbitrary rule under the auspices of colonialism. Democratic governance based on adult suffrage, freedom of expression and association constitute a necessary burden to the continent. Bad governance is neither inherent in the culture or traditions of the people of poor countries, nor a product of poverty. It is rather the result of the ways in which state authority in the south has been constructed and maintained economically and politically by the Global North. The policies and practices of northern governments and the pattern of international economic transactions help sustain poor governance in the south. This has reduced the capacity of governments to determine and control events in their countries, and thus their accountability and responsiveness to their people.

Furthermore, globalisation introduces anti-developmentalism on governance by declaring the state irrelevant or marginal to the developmental effort. Development strategies and policies imposed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank to third world countries focus on stabilization and privatization, rather than growth, development and poverty eradication, leading to greater poverty and inequality and undermining the ability of the people to participate effectively in the political and social processes in their countries.

Realizing this problem, the African Union through its Assembly of African leaders committed itself to the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), pushing for good governance and democracy in the whole continent particularly in the 21st century.

4.4 Globalisation and Socio-Cultural Challenges in Africa

Socio-culturally, globalisation has brought about cultural imperialism and domination to Africa. African countries are rapidly losing their cultural identity and therefore their ability to

interact with other cultures on an equal and autonomous basis, borrowing from other cultures only those aspects that meet their requirements and needs.

Cultural imperialism is the practice of promoting, distinguishing, separating or artificially injecting the culture or language of one nation into another. It is usually the case that the former is a large economically and militarily powerful nation while the latter is a smaller, less important one. Cultural imperialism may take a form of forceful imposition of a particular culture on a people or voluntary and gradual embracing of foreign culture by individuals.

Several studies have revealed how globalisation came into Africa through slavery and colonialism which resulted in heavy loss in terms of human and material resources to Africa. The modern-day globalisation is powered by information which has rightly been described as the vehicle through which culture is transmitted from one generation to another. With the new information environment, the pace at which culture is exported from one place to another has increased dramatically. Countries with superior digital power are favored by the new information environment. Thus, the exchange of cultural information does not occur on a level playing ground and Africa remains at the receiving end.

Liberalization and privatization created opportunities for multinational companies with their vast political and economic resources to install themselves as key players in the critical sectors of the economy. With privatization, these companies took over investment in social services such as health care, education, power supply and telecommunication among others. The control of access to education means that education became costly beyond the reach of many African children, thereby laying the foundation of cultural imperialism.

4.5 The Challenges of Globalisation and Africa's Regional Integration

The challenges posed by globalisation made it necessary for the continent to come together as a body under the umbrella of the African Union as this was perceived to give them a solid voice at the international level. The belief was that a political and economic African Union could provide the strength and cohesiveness needed to solve Africa's many problems and resist modern expansion by powerful western countries seeking primarily to take resources from less developed countries.

Regional integration has been considered the most appropriate measure to fight the challenges of globalisation in developing countries due to their nature in terms of economic output. Still, it has become imperative that if Africa is to survive the current challenges posed by globalisation, African states must come together and strengthen the functions, policies and activities of the African Union to minimize the adverse effects of globalisation while harnessing whatever benefits are available for continental development.

4.6 The African Union Efforts towards Meeting these Challenges

4.6.1 The NEPAD Initiatives

The New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) was established to promote good governance, democracy, economic reform and sustainable development in Africa. It seeks to provide a framework through which African states can collectively address developmental challenges and integrate effectively into the global economy.

4.6.2 The African Peer Review Mechanism (APRM)

The African Peer Review Mechanism (APRM) was created as a voluntary instrument for self-monitoring by member states of the African Union. It aims to promote good governance in political, economic and corporate spheres.

African Peer Review (APR) Forum: a committee of all participating Member States' Heads of State and Government. The Forum is the APRM's highest decision-making authority.

APR Panel: appointed eminent people with the responsibility of ensuring the Mechanism's independence, professionalism and credibility. Panel members are selected and appointed by the Forum.

APR Secretariat: provides technical, coordinating and administrative support services to the APRM. At the national level, country guidelines call for members to put structures in place to facilitate effective implementation of the APRM.

In addition, the APRM has support agreements with Africa-based institutions designated as strategic partners including the African Development Bank (ADB), UN Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Regional Bureau for Africa.

4.7 Conclusion

Globalisation is an international phenomenon which is gradually bringing the world together through socio-economic, political and cultural integrations. Unfortunately, however, it is doubtful whether African countries are ready for the challenges these integrations pose. This is because globalisation is driven by information and communication technology and trade liberalization which are relatively new to Africa. This has resulted in underdevelopment, poverty, inequality and cultural imperialism.

This is an ugly development which the African Union, policy makers and Africans at large must respond to, if they truly hope to position their societies and economies to meet the demand of the 21st century.

CHAPTER FIVE

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter summarizes the main findings of the study. It also offers some recommendations to the African Union and policy makers on how to address the challenges facing Africa and regional integration especially those brought by globalisation.

5.2 Summary

Globalisation is not a new concept, having surfaced in various forms throughout history. It is a multi-dimensional concept covering areas including economic, political, social, cultural spheres and so on. It is widely considered to be beneficial to developed nations but, however, poses a lot of challenges to Third World countries, particularly those in Africa.

Developed countries with their advanced technology and a network of transnational corporations are gradually conquering the world once again in a new form of colonialism. Capturing the essence of globalisation in the present world order, AINA (1997) asserted that:

“The world as we knew it even a couple of years ago remains no longer the same. Massive development in communication and technology, the restructuring of global capitalism, the collapse of the Soviet Union and the end of the Cold War, the dominant role of international financial institutions, transnational corporations and the ubiquitous presence of their agents, money and ideas along with changes in individual and corporate lifestyles, have all come together to create new conditions of intensity, proximity and even almost intimacy with what used to be external far away worlds.”

Globalisation has brought about economic marginalization of African states and reinforced their dependence on primary commodities whose prices are externally determined. It has intensified poverty, inequality and underdevelopment in Africa.

Politically, globalisation has weakened the sovereignty of African states and reduced their autonomy in decision-making, especially in economic and financial matters. Policies imposed by

international financial institutions have undermined the capacity of African governments to respond effectively to the needs of their citizens.

Socio-culturally, globalisation has promoted cultural imperialism, leading to erosion of African values and identity. The dominance of foreign culture, aided by technological advancement and information flow, has placed Africa at a disadvantage in the global cultural exchange.

In response to these challenges, African states pursued regional integration through the establishment of the African Union. The AU, together with its institutions such as NEPAD and APRM, represents Africa's collective response to the challenges posed by globalisation.

5.3 Recommendations

If Africa is to overcome the challenges of globalisation, African states must strengthen the institutions of the African Union and enhance cooperation among member states.

There is the need for African leaders to promote good governance, accountability and transparency to attract investment and foster sustainable development.

African states should diversify their economies, reduce dependence on primary commodities and promote industrialization.

There should be greater emphasis on education, technological development and capacity building to enable Africa to compete effectively in the global economy.

Regional economic communities should be strengthened to facilitate trade, economic integration and collective bargaining power in the international system.

5.4 Implication of the Findings

The findings of this study imply that globalisation has both opportunities and challenges for Africa. However, without strong institutions and collective action through the African Union, Africa may continue to experience marginalization in the global system.

It also implies that regional integration remains a viable strategy for African states to confront the adverse effects of globalisation and improve their bargaining power in international affairs.

5.5 Conclusion

Globalisation has had profound impacts on Africa in economic, political and socio-cultural spheres. While it has created opportunities for growth and development, it has also intensified inequality, poverty and marginalization.

The establishment of the African Union is a significant step towards addressing these challenges. However, more commitment is required from African leaders and member states to strengthen the Union and ensure that it effectively serves as a platform for sustainable continental development.

References

- Abubakar, G. (2001). *Globalisation, social sciences and Nigeria in the 21st century*. ABU Zaria Printing Press.
- African Union Commission & New Zealand Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade. (2015). *African Union handbook*. Crown Publishers.
- African Commission for Africa. (2000). *Globalisation, regionalism and Africa's development agenda*. UNCTAD.
- Agubuzu, L. O. (2002). *From the OAU to AU: The challenges of African unity and development in the twenty-first century*. Nigeria Institute of International Affairs.
- Aina, T. (1997). *Globalisation and social policy in Africa: Issues and research directions*. CODESRIA.
- Akinbola, A. (1999). Globalisation and economic development of emergent nation states: A comparative study of Thailand, Kenya and Taiwan. *MILD Journal*.
- Akokpari, A., Ndinga-Muvumba, A., & Murithi, T. (2008). *The African Union and its institutions*. University of Michigan Press.
- Asante, S. K. (2007). *Ghana and the promotion of Pan-Africanism and regionalism*. Ghana Academy of Arts and Sciences.
- Banjo, L. (2000). IMF, World Bank, WTO: The wicked machines of imperialism. *Sunday Tribune*, 19.
- Bello, W. (2001). *Calling for the reform of the WTO*. ABU Press Ltd.
- Biersteker, T. (1998, April 11). Globalisation and the models of operation of major institutional actors. *Oxford Development Studies*, 15–31.
- Cerry, P. (1994, February 24). The dynamics of financial globalisation: Technology, market structure and policy response. *Policy Sciences*, 20, 317–342.
- Charlick, R. (1997). *The globalisation of poverty: Impacts of IMF and World Bank reforms* (2nd ed.). Cornell University Press.

- Frank, A. G. (1969). *The development of underdevelopment*. Bobbs-Merrill.
- George, P. (1956). *Pan-Africanism or communism: The coming struggle for Africa*. Dodson Books.
- Giddens, A. (1999). *The consequences of modernity*. Stanford University Press.
- Held, D., McGrew, A., Goldblatt, D., & Perraton, J. (1999). *Globalisation and global governance*. Polity Press.
- Herbst, J. (2007). *Africa and the challenge of globalisation*. Icfai University Press.
- Khor, M. (2001). *Rethinking globalisation: Critical issues and policy choices*. Zed Books.
- Lavergne, R. (2010). *Regional integration and cooperation in West Africa: A multi-dimensional perspective*. ECOWAS Commission.
- MacEwan, A. (1990). *What's new about the new international economy*. University of Massachusetts.
- Madunagu, E. (1999). Globalisation and its victims. *The Guardian*, 5.
- Martin, K. (2001). *Rethinking globalisation: Critical issues and policy choices*. Zed Books.
- Mbaku, J. M., & Saxena, S. C. (Eds.). (2004). *Africa at the crossroads: Between regionalism and globalisation*. Praeger Publishers.
- Mick, M. (2003). Political underdevelopment: What causes bad governance? *PMR*, 3, 13–14.
- Mowlana, H. (1998). Globalisation of mass media: Opportunities and challenges of societies. *Cooperation South*, 2, 22–39.
- Mule, H. (2000, May 17). Challenges to African governance and civil society. *African Notes*, 7–9.
- Murithi, T. (2005). *The African Union: Pan-Africanism, peace building and development*. Ashgate Publishing Ltd.
- Otokhine, E. (2005). Internet strengthens cultural imperialism. *The Comet*, 21.

- Oyejide, T. (2003). Africa trade prospects in a globalisation era. *Cooperating South*, 2.
- Philippe De Lombaerde, & Van Langenhove. (2007). *Regional integration, poverty and social policy*. Princeton University Press.
- Rodney, W. (1981). *How Europe underdeveloped Africa*. Bogle-L'Ouverture & Tanzania Publishing House.
- Samuel Mkinda, & Okumu, F. W. (2006). *The African Union: Past and future governance challenges*. Routledge.
- Tando, Y. (1998). *Globalisation and African options (Part one)*. African Association of Political Science.
- Thompson, V. (1969). *Africa and unity: The evolution of Pan-Africanism*. Longmans.
- Tilley, L. (2000). AU marks new dawn for Africa. In *African Union Summit* (pp. 13–25). AU Commission.
- Tomlinson, J. (1996). Cultural globalisation: Placing and displacing the West. *European Journal of Development Research*.
- Krugman, P. (1995). Globalisation and the inequality of nations. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 110, 857–880.
- Van de Walle, N. (2001). *African economies and the politics of permanent crisis (1979–1999)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wikipedia. (2016, October 11). Cultural imperialism. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cultural_imperialism
- Wikipedia. (2016, October 11). Prebisch–Singer hypothesis. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prebisch-Singer_hypothesis
- Yunusa, Y. (2004). *Globalisation, ICTs and the new imperialism: Perspectives on Africa in the global electronic village*. ABU Printing Press.
- Yusuf, A. (1994). *Democratization in Africa: African perspective*. Abuja COS.